

THERMAL AGING REDUCTION IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Polymer Matrix Composites (PMCs) degrade due to both physical and chemical aging, especially at elevated and high temperatures (HTs). Applications where PMCs are exposed to HTs may require remediation approaches to reduce the impact of thermal aging. This paper presents recent research that offers one approach to reduce the impact of thermal aging of hybrid glass/carbon fiber epoxy matrix composite rods utilized in novel high voltage (HV) transmission lines employing Polymer Core Composite Conductors (PCCC), and in other HT applications employing PMCs.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Aluminum Conductor Composite Core (ACCC®), a type of PCCC offered by CTC Global, (Figure 1) offers significant advantages over traditional Aluminum Conductor Steel Reinforced (ACSR) lines. Because of the PMC core's superior specific strength and stiffness, additional and fully annealed aluminum can be used as the conductor component, reducing electrical resistance and increasing transmission efficiency. Due to the negative coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of carbon fiber, these transmission lines sag significantly less at high temperatures than ACSR lines and thus can be operated at higher temperatures. The combination of these improvements allows 2-3 times the amount of current to be transmitted through the same size and weight lines, reducing the need to add new lines, towers and other transmission structures as electrical demands increase.

Figure 1. ACCC Conductor

Research in our lab has shown that the flexural and fatigue properties of the ACCC composite core can be dramatically decreased by long term thermal aging at 180 °C [1-3]. Physical aging results in increasing residual stresses in the composite [2] and chemical aging leads to surface oxidation and a potential new source of flexural failure [1-3].

In a recently published paper [3], it was shown that applying an oxidation barrier coating significantly improves the thermal aging performance of the composite core at high temperatures which can be expected in service. In the initial experiment performed by Burks et al [1], a 4-point bend test showed an initial dropoff in flexural load at failure of about 10% after 3 months of aging at 180 °C and a gradual continuing decline through 9 months of aging (23% drop). However, after 12 months, there was a significant reduction in the load at failure of 74% of the original unaged value. In [3], a fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) based coating was applied and the experiment was repeated to assess the impact of this oxygen barrier. The difference was dramatic. While the initial declines through 9 months were similar to the uncoated rods, there was no dramatic decline at 12 months.

The authors in [3] attributed the the initial dropoffs in strength in the first 9 months to increased residual stresses due to physical aging which occurred in both the coated and uncoated samples. The dramatic dropoff in flexural strength after 12 months of thermal aging of the uncoated rods was attributed to chemical aging (thermal oxidation) on the surface of the coated rods leading to large enough cracks that stress concentrations at these cracks became the initiation point for flexural failure of the rods. This view was supported by a finite elements model that demonstrated a shear stress concentration at the tip of a small notch simulating the chemical aging damage on the surface (see Figure 2). The finite elements model identified the stress concentration in the notch near the surface to be the maximum shear stress point in the glass fiber composite section of the hybrid rod. The coated samples did not have this same chemical aging and thus the strength decline was still predominantly caused by physical aging.

Figure 2. Shear stress along radial line in horizontal plane between load and support pins. Shear stress concentrations at notch tip are higher than rest of glass region

2 HIGH TEMPERATURE ACCELERATED AGING

2.1 Overview

As a follow-up to the experiments conducted in [1,3], coated and uncoated ACCC composite rod specimens were aged at 200 °C for 3, 6, and 12 months and flexural tests were performed in a four-point bend test apparatus.

2.2 Method

Uncoated ACCC rods were received from the Western Area Power Administration (WAPA) from an unused full conductor reel. These samples arrived in 5 foot sections. The hybrid composite cores have an outer diameter of 9.53 mm with the carbon section having a diameter of roughly 6.8 mm. Some of the hybrid cores were sent to E.L. Stone Company who applied a proprietary fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) based coating with a thickness of approximately 25 microns. The rods were lightly sandblasted prior to the application of the coating to improve adhesion. As noted in [3] no evidence of surface damage was visible even under 100x optical imaging.

Coated and uncoated rods were cut to lengths of 28 cm. The ends of each rod were capped with an RTV sealant to prevent longitudinal oxidation from the ends. Samples were aged at 200 °C under atmospheric conditions. Three samples of coated and uncoated rods for each aging duration were produced and tested. Samples were heated and cooled at a rate of 5 °C per minute to reduce the risk of thermal shock.

Samples were tested in a four-point bend test fixture designed by Burks et al [1]. As suggested in [1], samples were loosely wrapped with Teflon tape at the contact point with the loading pins to prevent transverse crushing. The load rate was 3 mm/ minute. Center point displacement measures, using an LVDT, and force measures were taken at a 20 Hz sampling rate. Crosshead displacement continued until failure of the samples.

Figure 3. Unaged ACCC core samples. As received (top) and coated (bottom)

Figure 4. Aged ACCC core samples. As received (top) and coated (bottom)

2.3 Results

Figure 3 shows as received ACC core rods before and after coating. Figure 4 shows the rods after 12 months of aging at 200 °C.

As in the prior experiments [1-3], all samples aged at 200 °C failed in shear in the horizontal midplane of the rods in the four-point bend test. Table 1 shows the average load at failure and flexural modulus of the three samples tested for each aging duration.

		3	6	12
Load at failure	Unaged			
	200 °C Coated	4598	2357	2067
	200 °C Uncoated	4598	2959	2364
Flexural Modulus	Unaged			
	200 °C Coated	82.5	79.9	80.3
	200 °C Uncoated	80.9	80.4	81.7

Table 1. Load at failure and flexural modulus of aged samples

2.4 Discussion

As noted in Table 1, core rods aged at 200 °C lose flexural strength with increased aging times, but generally maintain or improve their stiffness. It is believed that stiffness increases with post-curing

Figure 5: Flexure load at failure for ACCC rods after specified aging time and temperature

(the rods are manufactured with a rapid curing cycle in a pultrusion process) and from the effects of physical aging. However, physical aging also increases the residual stresses in the rods as demonstrated by Middleton et al [2]. As aging time increases, so do the residual stresses leading to a lower flexure load at failure. Thus, we see a steady drop in the flexure load at failure.

The situation becomes more interesting as a comparison is made to the results of aging at 180 °C from [1] and [3]. Figure 5 shows the flexure loads at failure for the samples aged at 180 °C and 200 °C. From this figure, it can be seen that initially the loads at failure drop faster for 200 °C aging than for 180 °C. Also, in both cases the load at failure continues to steadily decline as aging time increases

through the first six months (and in fact 9 months for rods aged at 180 °C, although that data is not presented here).

However, at 12 months, the uncoated rods aged at 180 °C show a dramatic dropoff in the load at failure, a reduction that is not seen in the coated rods aged at 180 °C or in the coated or uncoated rods aged at 200 °C. It is believed that this steep dropoff for the 180 °C uncoated rods is due to thermal oxidation of the surface of the rods producing cracks large enough to create stress concentrations that can be the initiation point for shear failures. This chemical aging does not occur on the coated rods aged at 180 °C because the coating acts as an oxidation barrier. Thus, as presented in [3] we do not see this same dramatic dropoff in the flexure load at failure. Figure 6 shows a comparison of the changes in flexural modulus for the four aging temperature/coating conditions. Here again we see a dramatic dropoff for the 180 °C 12 month aged rods and again it is believed that chemical aging is responsible for destroying enough of the surface matrix to reduce the stiffness of the whole material.

Figure 6: Flexural modulus for ACCC rods after specified aging time and temperature

So, why do we not see this same dropoff for uncoated rods aged at 200 °C? Barjasteh et al [4] performed oxidation experiments on the core rods and modeling of the oxidation reaction in the epoxy at both 180 °C and 200 °C. What they found was that the depth of oxygen penetration was actually lower at the higher temperature of 200 °C than it was for 180 °C. From visual inspection of aged samples they found the oxidation thickness was 155 μm for aging at 180 °C but only 110 μm for aging at 200 °C. This surprising result was reinforced by their numerical model of the oxidation reaction. The authors of this paper have reproduced the Barjasteh model and its results are displayed in Figure 7 where the oxygen concentration is displayed as a function of the depth below the surface after 100 hours of aging. There is negligible change in the modeled oxygen concentration beyond 100 hours at either temperature.

Basically, thermal oxidation occurs through a reaction diffusion mechanism. While both the diffusion rate and the reaction rate of oxygen with the epoxy polymer (consumption rate) escalate with increasing temperature, the consumption increases at a faster rate than the diffusion so the oxygen does not penetrate as far into the bulk of the polymer, unless as Barjasteh points out there is significant cracking or surface erosion which would allow deeper oxygen penetration.

Figure 7: Oxygen concentration as a function of distance from the surface

Thus, our working hypothesis is that the deeper oxygen penetration at the lesser 180 °C temperature eventually creates cascading damage on the surface leading to a dramatic drop in flexural stiffness. The cracks on the surface also create an initiation point for shear failure which reduces the flexural load at failure. Less chemical aging occurs at the higher 200 °C temperature and these same dramatic effects are not observed.

3 CONCLUSIONS

There are significant advantages in utilizing high temperature low sag conductors such as the ACCC for electrical transmission lines. To take full advantage of these conductors and ensure their long term in-service effectiveness even if utilized at 180 °C for long periods of time, certain enhancements may be necessary. One possible enhancement is to include coatings on the surface of the hybrid core rods to protect them from thermal oxidation that reduces flexural properties. Recent and ongoing research is demonstrating the effectiveness of this technique. Additional testing at 200 °C demonstrates that more rapid consumption of oxygen in the polymer matrix at the higher temperature leads to reduced oxygen penetration and no dramatic dropoff in the flexural load at failure. This study offers additional evidence that thermal oxidation causes surface damage leading to a dramatic reduction in the flexural load at failure in uncoated rods aged for 12 months at 180 °C.

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